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A thermographical method to evaluate the performance of magnetic nanoparticles in hyperthermia through spatio-temporal temperature profiles[†]

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The evaluation of the specific power absorption of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) in media with viscosities similar to those of the intracellular environment is key to improve their performance on *in vitro* magnetic hyperthermia (MH) experiments. A gel with adjustable viscosity such as polyacrylamide gel (PAG) can serve as a phantom to emulate intracellular viscosity for this matter. In this work, iron oxide MNPs with 26 nm average diameter were coated with glucose and dispersed into a 8 % polyacrylamide gel phantom at a nanoparticle concentration of 0.5 % wt. Power absorption experiments were performed under ac magnetic fields with amplitude of 400 Oe and a frequency of 350 kHz. The temperature evolution was monitored through a thermographic camera and spatio-temporal profiles were obtained from the videos. The analysis of these profiles allowed us to gather information on the heat flux during the magnetic hyperthermia experiments. We obtained considerable temperature increments for MNPs dispersed in cytosol-viscosity emulating medium and estimated the specific power absorption spatio-temporally.

1 Introduction

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) are thoroughly characterized in organic solvents and water before carrying out magnetic hyperthermia (MH) experiments *in vitro*. However, the specific power absorption (SPA) obtained in these media does not reflect the performance in cell cultures. Many authors report that the problem is that intracellular viscosity is considerably higher than that of the test media^{1–3}, and others blame the agglomeration promoted by the cellular environment^{2,3}. To counter it, MNP anisotropy is often lowered to warrant magnetic relaxation through Néel's mechanism⁴ and agglomerates are shaped into anisotropic arrangements to increase the SPA of the system⁵. However, shaping the agglomerates often involves placing the cell culture into large DC fields, which is inconvenient when thinking on the final medical application.

It is fundamental to characterize the MNP system in media sim-

ilar to that of the application to be able to optimize the experiments for these conditions. There are different characteristics of the cellular environment that could be mimicked into a phantom: conductivity, viscosity, ion concentrations, etc^{6–8}. From these, the one that is crucial for determining magnetic relaxation and thus the SPA is viscosity^{9,10}, which highlights the importance of emulating it¹¹. Polyacrylamide gel (PAG) viscosity can be tuned by varying acrylamide concentration during preparation¹².

The viscosity of the cellular environment is diverse: going from 1 to 10 cP, depending on the cell type and intracellular localization¹³. The cytosol is ~ 1.5 times more viscous than water¹⁴ and its viscosity is in the range of those covered by PAGs¹², thus they are great cytosol-phantom candidates for the study of MNP systems.

Another key aspect is the way in which we characterize the performance of MNPs: SPA can be calculated through calorimetric and magnetic measurements^{15–17}. When the calorimetric method is used, the SPA is calculated through the temperature increment in time (dT/dt) at the start of the MH experiment, when the system can be assumed quasi-adiabatic. Heat losses modify dT/dt and make the determination of the SPA of the system a challenging task, since they depend on the equipment used for the measurements, room temperature and the morphology of the sample. Many reports have assessed SPA through the correction of the heat losses^{16,18–20} but there are no reports on the assessment of the distribution of SPA values on the sample.

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There has been numerous reports of temperature spatial profiles in magnetic fluids, tissue phantoms and tumors, obtained both experimental^{21,22} and theoretically^{23,24}, caused by heat losses to adjacent tissue, increased tumor vascularization and blood perfusion^{24–26}. These heat losses are detrimental because the effective SPA is significantly lower in some targeted areas but they are also desirable because they prevent the heating, thus the damage, of the surrounding healthy tissue^{27,28}.

To assess the temperature in this kind of experiments, a high-resolution infrared thermographic camera is often used^{21,22,29}, which allows to have the temperature spatial profiles as a function of time during a MH experiment. For this work, we prepared a PAG with dispersed MNPs and performed a MH experiment monitored by a thermographic camera. We developed a method to gather both spatial and temporal information from the obtained videos and analyzed not only temperature but heat flux and effective SPA of the system.

2 Experimental

2.1 MNP synthesis and characterization

Through the thermal decomposition of iron(III) acetylacetonate [Fe(acac)₃] in the presence of oleic acid and oleylamine, using dibenzylether as solvent (boiling point ~ 570 K) and a subsequent thermal treatment at 573 K, we obtained iron oxide MNPs with an average size of 26 nm and a standard deviation of 2 nm. The saturation magnetization at room temperature is $M_S = 71$ emu g⁻¹ (see ESI[†]).

2.2 MNP glucose coating

To change the hydrophobic nature of the synthesized MNPs, their oleic acid coating was removed with several methanol and acetone washes and then replaced by glucose coating obtained from the dispersion of uncoated MNPs with 10 times their mass in glucose in a pH=12 ammonia solution. The MNPs in this solution were magnetically separated and redispersed in milliQ water.

2.3 Polyacrylamide gel preparation

Three 8 % PAGs were prepared: a clean PAG without MNPs (blank), a PAG with a MNP concentration of 0.1 % wt and another one of 0.5 % wt. For this matter, we prepared an acrylamide/bisacrylamide solution (30/0.8 % w/v) and used an aliquot of 195 μ l with 200 μ l of 0.375 M Tris-HCl pH 8.8 buffer solution for each of them. Then we added 350 μ l of milliQ or milliQ water with ~ 0.8 or 4.0 mg of dispersed glucose-coated MNPs, respectively. As the polymerization of acrylamide is given by a free-radical driven reaction³⁰, 55 μ l of ammonium persulfate (APS) was added as a free radical initiator and 6 μ l of N,N,N',N'-tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED) to stabilize the polymerization chain reaction³¹. This produces ~ 800 μ l of PAG in an acrylic sample holder with a diameter of 1.3 cm, as seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Images of the experimental setup with indications to the corresponding elements. The images represent a power absorption experiment conducted on a blank PAG and monitored through a thermographic camera placed into a tripod.

2.4 Thermographic camera measurements

The PAG phantom was centered into a coil with a water jacket with an inlet and an outlet for recirculating water at ~ 15 °C. A power absorption experiment was carried out on an *EASYHeat 5060* with an ac field of amplitude 400 Oe and a frequency of 350 kHz and was monitored through a *FLIR E50* thermographic camera placed into a tripod ~ 50 cm above the phantom, as seen in Fig. 1. The video recording consisted of the power absorption experiment followed by the shutdown of the magnetic field and the cooling of the phantom until the equilibrium (room) temperature was reached.

2.5 Video processing

Frames of the video were extracted at 10 s intervals [see Fig. 2(a)]. An interactive software was developed to transform the information in these images into calibrated grayscale profiles as a function of time. The software reads all frames as images and prompts the user to select the temperature scale and the PAG's region of interest ROI(x,y) in one of the frames [see Fig. 2(b)]. For this study, the ROI was taken as a rectangle that contains the center of the phantom. Moreover, once the ROI has been chosen, the user can interactively specify the placement of the sample holder wall in order to transform pixel values into distance by taking into account the PAG's dimension. The ROI is then converted into a matrix of gray value information and a grayscale profile is obtained by averaging y -values at a fixed x . To calibrate the gray values into temperature, the software performs the corresponding transformation with the previously selected temperature scale [see Fig. 2(c)].

Once calibrated, temperature profiles for each frame were interpolated to generate a consistent distance grid through them, which allows the generation of a raw temperature map as a function of distance and time [see Fig. 3(a)]. As the analysis of the data required it, the map was smoothed through a two-step process including: (a) a moving average smoothing and (b) a Gaussian blur filter [see Figs. 3(b-c)], which was implemented through the corresponding convolution masks.

Fig. 2 Scheme of the different steps in video processing software. (a) Frame extraction from the video. (b) Image of one frame from the video where the placement of the PAG with MNPs and the sample holder is indicated, as well as the temperature scale and ROI (shaded in yellow) that can be interactively selected by the user. (c) Process of obtaining a temperature profile from the 2D ROI (selected from 1 frame) through y -averaging and interactive calibration.

Fig. 3 (a) Raw temperature map (temperature as a function of distance and time) obtained from interpolated data from video frames. (b) Temperature map after a moving average smoothing and (c) consequent Gaussian blur filtering.

2.5.1 Important remarks

The thermographic camera used allowed the temperature scale to be settled before the experiment or the leave it in automatic mode (which means that the temperature scale can be updated on-the-go, while temperature increases). However convenient this might seem, the automatic mode presents a serious problem regarding temperature calibration because the update rate is lower than the frame rate. The temperature scale was settled to a fixed temperature range (from 290 to 308 K) and the video experiment time was controlled in order to avoid surpassing the temperature limit.

While the camera was placed into a tripod and carefully aligned, if there were any parallax problems left in the final video, the software allows the user to rotate the frames in order to select the ROI in the direction that is perpendicular to that of maximum deviation.

Finally, the position and distance calibration of the ROI is maintained throughout the analysis, which is crucial to avoid unwanted noise in the final temperature map.

2.6 Specific heat determination

A differential scanning calorimeter *TA Instruments Q2000* was used to measure heat flux rate. The specific heat of a blank PAG and PAGs with MNPs at a concentration of 0.1 and 0.5 % wt was obtained by following the classical Three-Step Procedure³² that involved the measurement of the baseline, a sapphire standard and the samples. The ramps used were 2, 5 and 10 K/min and the refrigeration of the oven was attained with a nitrogen flux of 50 ml/min. The measurements were carried out for a temperature range going from 283 to 308 K. At least 2 determinations were made for each condition.

2.7 Thermal conductivity

3 Results

The temperature maps corresponding to the power absorption experiments performed with 8 % PAGs with MNPs at a concentration of 0.1 and 0.5 % wt are shown in Fig. 4(a) alongside the one from the blank. The ac field was turned on at $t = 60$ s for the 3 experiments. The maps are presented as temperature increment ΔT as a function of time t and distance r measured from the center of the PAG, were $\Delta T = T - T_{eq}$. The equilibrium temperature T_{eq} was calculated by averaging temperature data from 0 to 60 s, for all points inside the phantom.

From the comparison of the maps, it is evident that no significant temperature increment is presented for the blank, contrary to the PAGs with MNPs dispersed. For these last PAGs, a temperature increment of ~ 12 °C was attained in ~ 260 s for the 0.1 % wt MNP concentration and ~ 100 s for 0.5 % wt, evidencing that

a larger amount of MNPs can heat the medium faster.

Fig. 4 Increment of temperature maps for powerabsorption experiments performed in (a) a blank PAG, and PAGs with MNPs at a concentration of (b) 0.1 and (c) 0.5 % wt. The black dotted line indicates the time at which the ac field was switched off and the cooling of the sample begins.

It also can be seen that the temperature spatial distribution is approximately symmetric with respect to the center of the sample, which is coherent with the axial symmetry of the experimental setup (see Fig. 1). However, it is clearly noticeable that, for a given time, the temperature increase rate is not the same for the different points in the sample. In fact, temperature increases faster for the center of the PAG and slower near the sample holder walls, which could evidence that heat losses are not only due to the the sample being exposed at the surrounding environment

through the open top of the sample holder but also through its walls.

To rule out a possible dependence of the specific heat c_p of the PAGs with temperature, several measurements were made in blank PAGs and PAGs with MNPs at a concentration of 0.1 and 0.5 % wt as a function of temperature for different ramps. The results for all of these PAGs were $c_p = (4.1 \pm 0.1) \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$, showing no temperature of MNP concentration influence in the value of the specific heat of the samples in the working temperature range.

This last remark allows the evaluation of the energy liberated to the media normalized by the mass of MNPs in the sample m_{MNPs} by calculating $E = mc_p \Delta T / m_{\text{MNPs}}$, where m is the PAG's mass. The corresponding maps are presented in Fig. 5(a-b)] for the PAGs with MNPs, along with maps for its time derivative.

It is evidenced by comparing the data obtained for the power absorption experiment and the cooling of the samples that temperature-increase and cooling rates are not the same. In fact, this can be seen clearer in the time derivative map (see Fig. 5(c-d)). Moreover, from the cooling part of these maps we can obtain the power lost to the surroundings. When the

the difference between the samples with MNP concentration 0.1 and 0.5 % wt is strikingly notorious in terms of the

4 Conclusions

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Fig. 5 (a-b) Energy E , (c-d) time derivative $\frac{dE}{dt}$ (at fixed distance r) and (e-f) spatial derivative dE/dx (at fixed time t) maps for power absorption experiments performed in PAGs with MNPs at a concentration of 0.1 and 0.5 % wt, correspondingly. Black open dots represent the points with maximum $|dE/dx|$ at a given t .

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